

THE INFLUENCE OF MOTIVATION AND WORK FACILITIES ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE: STUDY ON ACADEMIC STAFF OF THE FACULTY OF ADMINISTRATIVE SCIENCE, UNIVERSITAS BRAWIJAYA

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to find out how significant and influential it is on employee performance from two variables, namely the motivation variable (x1) and the work facility variable (x2). The dominant-less dominant mix method is being used in this study at Universitas Brawijaya's academic division of the Faculty of Administrative Science. An explanatory research approach is being used, using the entire population as a sample of 35 employees using linear regression data analysis techniques duplicates and interviews. From the results of the analysis, it can be concluded that motivation and work facilities simultaneously have a significant influence on employee performance. This is evident from the F test where the data can be seen that the F value is $7.968 > 3.28$ (F table) and with a significant F of 0.002 where the significance is smaller or less than 0.05, thus it is found that motivation (x1) and facilities (x2) have an influence on performance (y). Of course, this was also justified by the related party in the interview who said that motivation and work facilities are very important, especially in supporting activities in the academic section. Without motivation at work, of course, employees will be reluctant to do work because of the rolling of the assignment letter given, whereas without facilities that support data input activities, etc. in academic activities, it will be very difficult to work on and will take a long time.

KEYWORDS

Motivation, Facilities, Performance

INTRODUCTION

As the main factor that drives public and private organizations, humans are a very important part of the running of an organization. According to Nawawi (2016), human resources are defined as driving components that work in an organizational environment. Later these human resources will interact with each other to be able to work together in order to achieve the vision and mission goals of the organization that have been initiated. Because later it is human resources that will move in order to solve problems and find solutions to problems that exist within the organization. Often we know the resources that drive the organization we call employees. In an organization or company in assessing how human resource processes interact with each other, it is seen from the performance aspects that have been evaluated. Performance is a description of the level of achievement of the implementation of an activity program or policy in realizing the goals, objectives, vision and mission of the

organization as outlined through the strategic planning of an organization according to (Moeherino, 2012). Indirectly explained that the success or failure of an organization or company is largely determined by the interaction of the employees in it. Of course, there are many factors that influence the performance itself, both internal and external.

We often know this as motivation. Motivation is a form of enthusiasm and encouragement that exists in humans or in an employee both in terms of completing work, interacting, and learning new things. According to a pinder, work motivation is defined as a series of energetic forces originating from within and from outside the individual, to initiate work-related behavior, and to determine its form, direction, intensity, and duration (Pinder, 2008). Motivation is something that belongs to the internal part of an employee, because without motivation the work and responsibilities that are taught will not be completed. In addition to motivation, other factors that are no less important than motivation are facilities. The facilities themselves are classified as external factors that come from employees whose existence is provided by the organization or company where they work. Facilities are defined as one of the factors supporting the work of an employee in carrying out tasks assigned by a company, good work facilities with appropriate instruments can support employee performance to be more conducive so as to make work more effective and efficient (Hasibuan, 2014). Work facilities provided by companies or organizations are a form of remuneration to employees in non-cash form that can be enjoyed individually or in groups (Mulyapradana & Hatta, 2016).

We all know that a university is a form of public organization in which apart from pursuing learning activities there are also other academic activities such as academic activities. Universitas Brawijaya, which is one of the well-known universities with one of the Faculties of Administrative Sciences, also has academic staff who work for the continuity of other academic activities.

Figure 1. Number of Undergraduate Students of Universitas Brawijaya (UB) By Faculty and Gender (Person)

Fakultas di Universitas Brawijaya	Jumlah Mahasiswa S1 Universitas Brawijaya (UB) Menurut Fakultas dan Jenis Kelamin (Orang)					
	Laki-Laki		Perempuan		TOTAL	
	2020	2021	2020	2021	2020	2021
Fakultas Hukum	1 411	1 457	1 438	1 556	2 849	3 013
Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis	2 029	2 254	2 380	2 742	4 409	4 996
Fakultas Ilmu Administrasi	1 824	2 111	3 069	3 878	4 893	5 989
Fakultas Pertanian	1 955	2 129	2 954	3 218	4 909	5 347
Fakultas Peternakan	1 573	1 667	1 238	1 264	2 811	2 931
Fakultas Teknik	3 057	3 466	1 917	2 380	4 974	5 846
Fakultas Ilmu Komputer	2 777	2 985	971	1 063	3 748	4 048
Fakultas Perikanan dan Ilmu Kelautan	1 525	1 685	1 963	2 228	3 488	3 913
Fakultas Matematika dan IPA	1 137	1 386	2 056	2 602	3 193	3 988
Fakultas Teknologi Pertanian	1 251	1 417	2 166	2 590	3 417	4 007
Fakultas Ilmu Sosial dan Ilmu Politik	1 979	2 110	2 887	3 329	4 866	5 439
Fakultas Ilmu Budaya	993	1 201	2 125	2 536	3 118	3 737
Fakultas Kedokteran	483	562	2 120	2 452	2 603	3 014

Source: "Number of Undergraduate Student", (2021)

Taking a look at the statistics from BPS Malang City reveals that the faculty with the most undergraduate students each year is where you will find the most of the FIA UB students.

which has a total of 5,989 pupils in 2021, up from 4,893 in 2020. While it can be seen from the data obtained by researchers in the pre-research it was found that the number of employees in the academic services section is a total of 35 people who are academic employees serving students at FIA. Seeing this, the researcher is interested in knowing how the motivation of FIA UB academic staff is in providing academic services, seeing the small number of academic employees with the large number of students to be served, besides that they also want to know how the influence of the work facilities provided by the organization in support the process of work efficiency in the academic section of FIA UB.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Human Resources

Nawawi (2016) argues that human resource management is a process to humanely utilize humans as workers, so that their physical and psychological potential functions optimally in an effort to achieve organizational or company goals. In addition, Kinggudu in Gomes (2003) defines human resource management as a form of increasing and empowering employees for the achievement of organizational, personnel and community goals and objectives.

Motivation

According to Hasibuan (2013), motivation can be interpreted as a driving force that is able to create the spirit of a person's work ethic so that they want to work together, work effectively, and integrate with all their efforts to achieve satisfaction. Another definition is also mentioned by Mathis in Budiyanto & Oetomo (2011) which states motivation is the desire within a person that encourages him/her to perform an action, where one often takes an action to achieve a particular goal. which encourages him to take an action, where a person often takes action to achieve certain goals). A person's work motivation can be measured using the 18 items WEIMS (Work Extrinsic and Intrinsic Motivation Scale), as has been done by Tremblay in his research. The WEIMS scale contains 1 item and assesses six types of motivation. The following is a description (Tremblay et al., 2009):

- a) Intrinsic motivation, including the pleasure of getting new experiences; satisfaction after successfully passing the challenge; and get satisfaction after completing a moderately difficult task;
- b) Integrated ideas/behaviors, including feeling part of the work being done; the work done is optional; and work is done part of life;
- c) Identified ideas/behaviors, including desired and achieved lifestyles; type of work is the planned career goals; and the work done is the goal that has been chosen;
- d) Institutionalized ideas/behavior, including increased self-confidence; Always wanted to be the best; and want to be a winner;
- e) External ideas/behavior, including sufficient salary; adequate income; and security at work; as well as
- f) Unexpected motivation, including the ability to manage multiple tasks; working conditions outside the main function; and high expectations of employees.

Work Facilities

According to Sedarmayanti (2018) work facilities are all tools and materials encountered, the surrounding environment where a person works, work methods, and work arrangements both as individuals and as a group. Facility is a means to expedite and facilitate the implementation of the work process. Indicators of own work facilities According to Faisal (2005) and Rika Okana (2017), facility indicators consist of:

- a. As needed
- b. Able to optimize work results
- c. Easy to use
- d. Speed up work processes
- e. The placement is laid out properly

Performance

Stolovitch and Keeps in Sinambela (2017) argue that performance is a set of results that can be achieved and refers to the act of achieving and implementing a job requested. Performance is an implementation of the balance theory, which describes that a person will show an optimal achievement if the person gets benefits and there is stimulation in his work fairly and rationally. The indicators used in assessing employee performance according to Mathis and Jackson (2010) and also in Muchtar (2016) are as follows:

- a. Quantity of Output
- b. Quality of Output
- c. Timeliness of Output
- d. Presence/Attendance on The Job
- e. Efficiency of Work Completed
- f. Effectiveness of Work Completed
- g. Ability to cooperate

RESEARCH METHODS

The research method is a scientific approach used to gather data for particular purposes (Sugiyono, 2015). The current study uses a quantitative explanatory research model. A quantitative research method, according to Sugiyono (2015), is a type of research methodology built on a positivist philosophy (visualization of an observed phenomena) and used to study and observe a population relative to a predetermined sample. The purpose of gathering data using statistical quantitative analysis research methods is to be able to test the hypotheses that have been developed. Faculty of Administrative Science, Universitas Brawijaya, which is situated in Malang City, was selected as the study's research site. While the research location is a location where researchers can record the precise status of the thing being examined in order to collect the required data. The Academic Service of FIA UB, which is housed in building B, was the research location selected for this project. The 35 participants or employees in the academic sector of the research sample were drawn from the whole population, which was employed as a saturated sample in the study. A simultaneous test is used to evaluate the hypothesis and collect data using multiple linear regression analysis and questionnaire methodologies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Motivation and work facilities are factors that support the implementation of one's duties. Motivation is one of the influences on the performance of an employee. Motivation can be said as a condition that drives employees who are directed to achieve organizational goals. Meanwhile, work facilities are facilities provided by the company to support the company's tone in achieving the gang goals determined by the controller. Of course, these two factors are interrelated and affect the performance of employees in an organization.

This can be seen from the average results of each item in the Y variable. It can be seen that the highest average with 35 respondents is in the statement item "I belong to an employee with high dedication at work". This can be seen from how each employee completes their respective duties, while the item statement "Employees are always present at meetings" of course performance can also be seen from the presence of an employee, in this case it can be seen in the activity of employees at each meeting by looking at employee absences.

Then also look at the results of the research seen in the results:

Multiple Linear Regression Test

Table 1. Multiple Linear Regression Test

Model		Coefficients ^a				Collinearity Statistics		
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
B	Std. Error	Beta						
1	(Constant)	2.476	.564		4.389	.000		
	Motivation	.749	.188	.660	3.984	.000	.760	1.315
	Facility	.377	.174	.359	2.169	.038	.760	1.315

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Source: Data Processed by Researchers, 2023

Based on the table on multiple linear regression, it can be seen that the constant value is 2.476 while for the value of X1 (motivation) it is 0.749 and the value of X2 (facility) is 0.377. In multiple linear regression, the constant value is 2.476 and for the value of X1 (motivation) is 0.749, the value of X2 (facilities) is 0.377, so the regression equation formed is :

$$Y = 2.476 + 0.749X_1 + 0.377X_2 + e$$

- The constant value of Y (Softskill) is 2.476 which states that if the variables X1 (motivation) and X2 (facilities) are equal to zero (0), then Y (performance) is 2.476.
- The X1 coefficient (motivation) is 0.749, meaning that every time the X1 variable (motivation) increases by 1%, the performance increases by 0.749 (74.9%) or vice versa, every time there is a decrease in X1 (motivation) by 1%, the performance decreases by 0.749 (74, 9%).
- The X2 coefficient (facilities) is 0.377, meaning that every time the X2 variable (facilities) increases by 1%, performance increases

Work motivation and facilities are factors that support the implementation of one's tasks, especially an employee who works to achieve goals. Motivation itself is a form of enthusiasm that comes from within a person while facilities are supporting infrastructure to assist in completing tasks or work. Judging from the results of the research, these two things have a significant influence on employee performance. From the results of 0.377 (37.7%) or vice versa every time there is a decrease in X2 (facilities) by 1%, it decreases by 0.377 (37.7%). From the description above it can be concluded that X1 (motivation), and X2 (facilities) effect on performance.

F Test (Simultaneous)

Table 2. F Test (Simultaneous)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.470	2	.735	7.968	.002 ^b
	Residual	2.951	32	.092		
	Total	4.420	34			
a. Dependent Variable: performance						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Facility, Motivation						

Source: Data Processed by Researchers, 2023

It can be seen in the simultaneous test results that the table displays a calculated F value of 7.968 > 3.28 (F_{table}) with an F significance of 0.002 (0.000 < 0.05) thus it can be concluded that simultaneously X1 (motivation) and X2 (facilities) have an effect to Y (performance), the hypothesis which states that there is an influence of motivation and work facilities on performance is accepted

CONCLUSION

The research concludes that simultaneously motivation and work facilities have a significant influence on employee performance. This is evident from the F test where the data can be seen that the F value is 7.968 > 3.28 (F table) and with a significant F of 0.002 which is significant is smaller or less than 0.05, thus it is found that motivation (x1) and facilities (x2) have an influence on performance (y).

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